

GENERALIZED QUASI-THREE DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE LAMINATES WITH STRAIN ACTUATORS

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ABSTRACT

A generalized quasi-three dimensional formulation based on the uniform deformation field which is consistent with the classical lamination theory is derived. Based on this formulation, finite element analysis is utilized and applied to the analysis of the composite laminates with strain actuators. The present analysis is shown to be useful for isolating the effect of free edge in the laminate under uniform loading. Stresses at the actuator/laminate interface are investigated and discussed from the light of delamination initiation and the effectiveness of the strain actuators. The effect of the coupling of bending and torsion is also evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Strain actuators such as the piezoelectric films, when combined with the fiber reinforced composite laminates, are of great practical interest for constituting the components of intelligent structures. The integration of the segmented elements of strain actuators and the laminates can allow the application of localized strains through which the deformation of the laminates can be controlled. Strain actuators can be placed into the laminates during the fabrication process which allows a flexibility of designs. The actuators can either be placed on the surface of the laminates or embedded at the interlayer of the laminates. Induced deformations can be used to suppress or excite the vibrations or to control the shapes of the laminated structures.

Attempts are made to provide shemes for analyzing the behavior of plates with strain actuators. One dimensional shear lag analysis was successfully utilized by Crawley and de Luis[1] to predict the extension and bending of the isotropic plate with surface bonded or embedded strain actuators. Dimitriadis et al.[2] extended this to the two dimensional analysis which was applied to the prediction of the vibration response. When the strain actuators are combined with the composite laminates, even a simple tensile strain actuated by the strain actuator can result in bending or torsional deformation of the laminate in addition to the pure extension, due to the anisotropic nature of the laminate. Thus the coupling of extension, bending and torsion must be taken into account to predict the precise behavior of these laminates with strain actuators. Lee[3] developed a theory for laminates with piezoelectric actuators to deal with the simultaneous bending, torsion, and extension, which is based on the classical lamination theory.

To investigate the more precise behavior of the laminates with actuators, it is desirable to make use of the finite element analysis. However a full three dimensional analysis introduces a large number of degrees of freedom resulting in vast size of memory and computational time. Shah et al.[4] introduced a generalized quasi-three dimensional finite element analysis developed by Chan and Ochoa[5] to effectively analyze the interlaminar stresses of the laminates with embedded piezoelectric layers. Their calculational effort was concentrated in the determination of the interface at which the piezoelectric layer should be placed, from the viewpoint of interlaminar stresses.

In the present paper, a generalized quasi-three dimensional finite element formulation is derived based on the displacement assumption of the uniform deformation field used in the classical lamination theory, the assumption which is different from that of Chan and Ochoa. The finite element analysis is then conducted based on this formulation for laminates with strain actuators.

FORMULATION

GENERALIZED QUASI-THREE DIMENSIONAL DISPLACEMENT FIELD

The classical lamination theory is based on the Kirchhoff's hypothesis which gives the following strain field for the laminate shown in Fig.1:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x(z) &= \bar{\varepsilon}_x + z\bar{\kappa}_x \\ \varepsilon_y(z) &= \bar{\varepsilon}_y + z\bar{\kappa}_y \\ \gamma_{xy}(z) &= \bar{\gamma}_{xy} + z\bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\bar{\varepsilon}_x$, $\bar{\varepsilon}_y$, $\bar{\gamma}_{xy}$ are the generalized strains, $\bar{\kappa}_x$ and $\bar{\kappa}_y$ are the curvatures and $\bar{\kappa}_{xy}$ is the twist of the laminate. The generalized quasi-three dimensional formulation derived here, which is suitable for the analysis of laminate, is based on the displacement field derived from the above uniform strain field. By introducing the additional local displacement components $U(y,z)$, $V(y,z)$ and $W(y,z)$, the displacement field assumed here is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \begin{bmatrix} u(x,y,z) \\ v(x,y,z) \\ w(x,y,z) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x x + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\gamma}_{xy}y + \bar{\kappa}_x xz + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}_{xy}yz \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y y + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\gamma}_{xy}x + \bar{\kappa}_y yz + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}_{xy}xz \\ -\frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}_x x^2 - \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}_y y^2 - \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}_{xy}xy \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} U(y,z) \\ V(y,z) \\ W(y,z) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} x & 0 & \frac{1}{2}y & xz & 0 & \frac{1}{2}yz \\ 0 & y & \frac{1}{2}x & 0 & yz & \frac{1}{2}xz \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{2}x^2 & -\frac{1}{2}y^2 & -\frac{1}{2}xy \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_x \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_y \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \\ \bar{\kappa}_x \\ \bar{\kappa}_y \\ \bar{\kappa}_{xy} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} U(y,z) \\ V(y,z) \\ W(y,z) \end{bmatrix} \equiv \mathbf{N}^0 \bar{\mathbf{e}} + \mathbf{U}(y,z) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

which incorporates tensile, shear, bending and torsional components of the laminate uniform deformation field.

Figure 1. Laminate with free edge

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

We start the finite element formulation here with the description of the basic equations. The strains can be written in terms of displacements as:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} &= [\varepsilon_x \quad \varepsilon_y \quad \varepsilon_z \quad \gamma_{yz} \quad \gamma_{zx} \quad \gamma_{xy}]^T \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right]^T \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The principle of virtual work can be written as:

$$\iiint_V \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \boldsymbol{\alpha} dV - \iint_S \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f} dS = 0 \quad (4)$$

and the linear constitutive equation is given as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0) \quad \text{or} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0 = \mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_x \quad \sigma_y \quad \sigma_z \quad \tau_{yz} \quad \tau_{zx} \quad \tau_{xy}]^T$, $\mathbf{u} = [u \quad v \quad w]^T$, $\mathbf{f} = [f_x \quad f_y \quad f_z]^T$ and $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{D}^{-1}$. S is the surface of the volume V .

In the finite element formulation, the local displacement $\mathbf{U}(y, z)$ is expressed by using the nodal displacement \mathbf{q} and the shape function matrix \mathbf{N} as follows:

$$\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{q} \quad (6)$$

By substituting Eqn (6) into Eqns (2) and (3), the displacements and the strains can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{N}^0 \bar{\mathbf{e}} + \mathbf{N}\mathbf{q} \quad (7)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{B}^0 \bar{\mathbf{e}} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{q} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{B}^0 and \mathbf{B} are the appropriate derivative matrices of \mathbf{N}^0 and \mathbf{N} , respectively. Substituting the above equations to the principle of virtual work, *i.e.* Eqn (4), and conducting an integration for a unit length in x -direction, following governing equation for a single element is obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{ee} & \mathbf{K}_{eq} \\ \mathbf{K}_{qe} & \mathbf{K}_{qq} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{e}} \\ \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_e \\ \mathbf{Q}_q \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_e \\ \mathbf{R}_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Figure 2. Definition of finite element and its boundaries for quasi-three dimensional analysis

where,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{ee} & \mathbf{K}_{eq} \\ \mathbf{K}_{qe} & \mathbf{K}_{qq} \end{bmatrix} = \iint_{S_x} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}^{0T} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B}^0 & \mathbf{B}^{0T} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B}^0 & \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} dS, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_e \\ \mathbf{Q}_q \end{bmatrix} = \iint_{S_x} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}^{0T} \\ \mathbf{B}^T \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_0 dS \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_e = \iint_S \mathbf{N}^{0T} \mathbf{f} dS, \quad \mathbf{R}_q = \int_C \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{f} dC \quad (11)$$

Here, S_x and C are the boundaries of the element as defined in Fig.2. By superimposing Eqn (9) for all the elements considered in the model, the governing equation of the finite element method is derived as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{K}}_{ee} & \underline{\mathbf{K}}_{eq} \\ \underline{\mathbf{K}}_{qe} & \underline{\mathbf{K}}_{qq} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\bar{\mathbf{e}}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{q}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{Q}}_e \\ \underline{\mathbf{Q}}_q \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{R}}_e \\ \underline{\mathbf{R}}_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where $(\underline{\quad})$ represents the superposition of the corresponding values. In Eqn (12), $\underline{\mathbf{R}}_e$ represents the external load vector whose components correspond to the components of the uniform generalized strain vector $\underline{\bar{\mathbf{e}}}$.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

INTERPRETATION OF THE METHOD

In order to interpret the characteristic nature of the present finite element method, the deformation of the symmetric, quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy composite laminate with the strain actuators $(\text{PZ}/45/0/-45/90)_s$, where PZ represents the piezoelectric layer, is analyzed. The piezoelectric layers are assumed to cover the whole laminate in this example. The thickness of a lamina and an actuator layer is set to be 0.13mm and 0.25mm, respectively. The material properties used throughout the present study are shown in Table.1.

The deformation state of the free edge region of the laminate under uniform bending moment M_x is

Table 1. Materials properties

Property	Carbon/Epoxy	Piezoelectric
E_1 (GPa)	133.1	63.0
E_2 (GPa)	12.4	63.0
G_{12} (GPa)	5.9	24.1
ν_{12}	0.30	0.31
t_{ply}, t_{piezo} (mm)	0.13	0.25

shown in Fig.3(a). The deformation state of the laminate cross section is dominated by an anticlastic bending as shown in the figure. This deformation state corresponds to the total displacements given in Eqn (2). One can disintegrate this deformation into the uniform and local displacements $N^0 \bar{e}$ and $U(y, z)$, respectively. The local displacement $U(y, z)$ is shown in Fig.3(b) in which the displacement is magnified by a factor of 100 as compared to Fig.3(a). As can be predicted from the nature of the present formulation, which is based on the uniform deformation field derived from the classical lamination theory, the local displacement represents the deviation of the deformed state from the analytical solution of the classical lamination theory. Thus the local displacement field is composed of the thicknesswise deformation and the disturbance of the deformation due to the existence of the free edge, both of which are not considered by the classical lamination theory. This is in consistency with the explanation of free edge interlaminar stresses described in [6], in which the cause of the interlaminar stresses is shown to be the deviation of the stress state from the classical lamination theory at the free edge region.

Figure 3. Deformation of the yz-cross section near the free edge of the laminate (PZ/45/0/-45/90)_s under external bending M_x .

Figure 4. Deformation of the yz -cross section near the free edge of the laminate $(PZ/45/0/-45/90)_s$ with free edge delaminations under negative actuator extension (delamination length=3.0mm).

The analysis is also conducted for the laminate under the actuation of the piezoelectric layers. In this case the actuator layers are delaminated from the free edge. The negative extensional strain is induced equally in both piezoelectric layers at the top and bottom surfaces. The deformed state is shown in Fig.4(a) and 4(b), in which again the total displacement and the local displacement are shown, respectively. Though the local displacement is not magnified in this case, the effect of the free edge is clear, as the existence of delaminations tends to exaggerate the effect. It should be noted that the delamination has no effect on the results derived from the classical lamination theory under uniform loading.

For the laminate with the partial coverage of the piezoelectric layer, the disintegration of the total displacements to the uniform and local contributions is not as clear. This is because the uniform deformation field represents the average value of the already non-uniform deformation field.

INTERLAMINAR STRESSES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF STRAIN ACTUATORS

From the practical point of view, the strain actuators may be placed partially to the laminate as strips. Whether the actuator strips are bonded on the surface or embedded in to the laminate, the stress concentration may take place at each end of the actuator strip. Even though the induced strains in the actuators are small, cyclic stress concentration can lead to the damage, *e.g.* delamination, of the components. It is thus important to know the stress level achieved at the interface region of the laminate/actuator system. At the same time the derived stress field at the interface can provide basic information of the effectiveness of the actuator strips.

The laminate stacking sequence is again set to be $([PZ]/45/0/-45/90)_s$, in which [PZ] represents the partial placement of the piezoelectric layer. The total width of the laminate $2b$ is 60mm and that of the actuator $2l$ is 30mm. The actuators at top and bottom surfaces are assumed to produce the antisymmetric strains respect to the y -axis, so as to induce bending in the y -direction. The distribution of the interfacial shear stress τ_{yz} is shown in Fig.5. In addition to the base actuator thickness of $t_{\text{piezo}}=0.25\text{mm}$, the case of $t_{\text{piezo}}=0.50\text{mm}$ is also considered. From Fig.5 the transient region is less than $0.1l=1.5\text{mm}$ for both cases, irrespective of the actuator thickness. Beyond this region at the tip of the actuator, the shear stress diminishes which implies that the actuation strain is fully transmitted to the base laminate.

The distribution of the normal stress σ_z for the same laminate is shown in Fig.6. The normal stress exhibits singularity at the edge, which suggests the use of the fracture mechanics parameters for predicting the damage extension. In the present case, as the laminate exhibits coupling between the bending and the torsion, the non-zero bending κ_x and the torsion κ_{xy} result from the introduction of the bending κ_y . The effect of constraining these bending and torsional deformations can be seen in Fig.6, in which the normal stresses σ_z under both constrained and unconstrained conditions of κ_x and κ_{xy} are shown. Although the difference of the two situations is not significant in this particular analysis, the use of the present generalized quasi-three dimensional formulation is suggested for the accurate prediction of the laminate behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

The quasi-three dimensional problem was generalized based on the uniform deformation which is consistent with that assumed in the classical lamination theory. Based on this generalization, the finite element method was formulated and applied to the analysis of composite laminates with strain actuators. The present analysis was shown to be useful for isolating the effect of free edge in the laminate under uniform loading. The normal stress achieved at the laminate/actuator interface under the strain actuation, which exhibited singular nature, can lead to the interfacial delamination to occur. The present finite element analysis can easily incorporate the virtual delamination extension calculation to obtain the energy release rates if required. The effect of the coupling of bending and torsion on the interlaminar stresses was also evaluated, though the effect was not significant in the present case.

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Figure 5. Shear stress τ_{yz} at the actuator/laminate interface under bending inducing actuation. ($([PZ]/45/0/-45/90)_s$, laminate width $2b = 60\text{mm}$, actuator width $2\ell = 30\text{mm}$)

Figure 6. Normal stress σ_z at the actuator/laminate interface under bending inducing actuation.